

Transfer learning for traffic state predictions in small and medium-sized cities

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Abstract In Flanders, 80% of the population resides in small and medium-sized cities, which face significant challenges in data-driven traffic management due to a lack of data. Although deep learning models surpass traditional methods for traffic state prediction, they require extensive data, often unavailable in these smaller cities. Transfer learning offers a potential solution by utilizing models trained in data-rich environments to enhance predictions in data-scarce regions. This ongoing research investigates the application of transfer learning for traffic state prediction in small and medium-sized cities. Preliminary tests in Greater Manchester and Lisbon under the TANGENT H2020 project have shown promising results. The next phase involves applying this technique to the Flemish city of Mechelen as part of the CitCom.ai project. The goal is to improve traffic state prediction in data-limited environments, thereby contributing to more efficient urban traffic management.

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1 Introduction

The EU is distinguished by its many small and medium-sized cities and towns. Almost half of all EU cities have populations between 50.000 and 100.000, inhabitants, and there are over 8.000 towns with populations ranging from 5.000 to 50.000. Together, these towns and cities are home to nearly 30% of the EU's population. In Flanders, this figure rises to over 80%. This means that the majority of Flemish citizens is scattered amongst 285 cities and communities, resulting in significant challenges for mobility data management, such as resource scarcity and data deficiencies.

A lack of mobility data limits the possibilities for a data-driven and proactive traffic management in small and medium-sized cities. As urban transportation systems evolve, accurately predicting traffic states, including active modes such as walking and cycling, and crowd dynamics, is crucial for efficient traffic management and proactive congestion response. Data-driven approaches can capture features in traffic data to forecast future states, and advancements in deep learning have led to models that surpass traditional statistical methods in performance. However, these approaches require a lot of data, which is often lacking in small and medium-sized cities.

This research introduces a novel approach for traffic state prediction in small and medium-sized cities, using transfer learning algorithms. Transfer learning can expedite the development of deep learning models in regions with limited historical traffic data, but its effectiveness for traffic forecasting requires further investigation [1, 2]. Transfer learning is not only a promising solution to the data scarcity of small and medium-sized cities, but it can also save significant effort, time, and resources needed to develop new prediction models, especially deep learning models. The transferability of deep learning models trained on data-rich cities to those with limited data is the key focus of this research.

This research will be conducted for the CitCom.ai project, in the medium-sized Flemish city of Mechelen, and will draw from the case study of Greater Manchester that was conducted for the TANGENT H2020 project.

Section 2 provides a background on traffic state predictions using deep learning models and transfer learning. Section 3 presents our results for two case studies of Greater Manchester and Lisbon, together with a possible path towards future research directions. Finally, section 4 provides a short conclusion.

2 Background

2.1 *Traffic state predictions*

Data-driven approaches capture features in traffic data, which can be used to predict the future traffic state. With the advancement of deep learning models in various

fields [3], researchers have developed multiple models for traffic supply forecasting, which surpassed traditional methods, e.g., statistical methods in performance. One of the early models DCRNN (Diffusion Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network) [4] presents a forecasting approach by integrating graph convolutional and recurrent neural networks which improved the state-of-the-art significantly. Meanwhile, other models are developed and improved the DCRNN model by introducing many different components like attention mechanisms for spatial and temporal aspects of the time series data [5, 6, 7].

The process of traffic state prediction is described in Fig. 1, and the different steps of the process are detailed below:

1. Input

Training a traffic state prediction model via data-driven approaches requires historical traffic data. The historical observations are used to train a model that predicts future traffic conditions. Historical data (e.g., time series of flows, speeds) coming from available traffic counters, floating vehicle data, etc., should preferably represent one year worth of data to incorporate all seasonal effects and is used for the training of the deep learning model. Real-time data, with a similar format, is used to provide traffic supply predictions in real-time based on the trained model.

Optionally, external features that influence traffic (e.g., weather data, road information like road type, number of lanes) can be collected, to be combined with historical and real-time traffic data. Note that the input of weather data should be the same granularity as the traffic data itself. Furthermore, it is required to have historical and real-time weather data, and a weather forecast.

2. Deep learning model

Deep learning modelling is performed on the collected input data. For testing, a traffic dataset is split in terms of training, validating, and testing. 70% of the historical data is used to train the deep learning model, 10% is used for validation, and 20% for testing purposes. Validation data helps in fine-tuning the model and prevents overfitting while testing data assesses its performance on previously

Fig. 1 Process of traffic supply forecasting with deep learning

unseen data and ensures its generalizability. For each dataset, model's hyperparameters should be optimized on the validation set to get the best results. The modelling task can be separated into two subtasks: spatial aggregation and temporal forecasting. Spatial aggregation is the task of aggregating the data from neighbouring nodes for the node of interest, and temporal forecasting is the task of predicting the future values of traffic states using the current values.

The model used in the preliminary tests in the remainder of this research, refers to a patent regarding traffic prediction, filed by imec and published with number US2024/0054321. It outperforms other methods in training time and has strong transfer learning capabilities. The model uses a convolution module to model the spatial-temporal relationships of the traffic data and an encoder-decoder architecture. The convolution module is applied to the time dimension which also considers the neighborhood and generates relation-based traffic data. The relation-based traffic data is then fed to an encoder to generate the fixed length vector latent representations. Afterwards, these representations are fed to the decoder to generate the predictions. The encoder and the decoder are both implemented using Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) like Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architecture.

3. Output

The output of these models are time series predictions for the future time steps.

2.2 *Transfer learning*

Transfer learning encompasses a range of machine learning techniques designed to transfer knowledge from a source domain, which is abundant in data, to a target domain, which is limited in data. This approach has proven highly successful in areas such as text classification and product recommendation. [8] acknowledges that the transfer learning approach has high potential for smart city applications, but existing algorithms cannot be blindly copied from other domains, because of the spatiotemporal patterns that exist in the urban domain. It defines three types of transfer learning for the smart city domain:

1. Cross-modality, which transfers between different data types. For example, social media data can be used as a proxy for crowd dynamics.
2. Cross-city, which transfers between different cities. For example, crowd dynamics of one city can be used as a proxy for the crowd dynamics of another city.
3. Cross-modality and cross-city, which transfers between modalities and between cities.

The overall procedure for transfer learning is shown in Fig. 2, a spatio-temporal deep learning model is first trained on the source dataset, with the objective to minimize the loss value. This procedure is called pretraining. In the pretraining step, the weights of the deep learning model are initialized randomly using initialization

methods such as Kaiming or He initialization. After the pretraining step, the weights of the model are used as initiate weights for training the same model using the target dataset. It might be needed to change some parts of the model, usually at the beginning or end of the model, based on the architecture of the model and training data shapes. Those altered weights are initiated randomly.

To address the data scarcity in small and medium-sized cities, transfer learning methods have been proposed for cross-city prediction models. For example, Region-Trans [9] concentrates on fine-tuning a source model, while [10] aims to selectively learn from the source city to better facilitate target fine-tuning. [11] proposed Graph Neural Networks for transfer learning in the urban environment, as the graph representation effectively captures the spatiotemporal patterns of the urban environment. The resulting transfer learning model with graph partitioning for traffic speed prediction (TEEPPEE) outperformed traditional traffic prediction models and transfer learning models without graph partitioning.

Although transfer learning has proven to be a promising technique for traffic predictions in small and medium-sized cities, few efforts have been made to date to combine transfer learning, and deep learning for traffic state predictions in real-world settings, with real-world data. To address this gap, we aim to develop and test this method on real-world datasets, coming from several Flemish cities for the CitCom.ai project. In a first phase, we conducted a series of tests for one of the case studies within the TANGENT project, specifically focusing on Greater Manchester and Lisbon.

Fig. 2 Process of traffic supply forecasting with transfer learning

3 Transfer learning for traffic state predictions in real-world settings

3.1 Case study of Greater Manchester

One of the use cases in the TANGENT project concentrates on the area of Greater Manchester. For this use case, a dataset of traffic counters is available, including speed bins and traffic flows (locations shown in Fig. 3). This data has been made available, with a resolution of 5 minutes and a duration of 13 months (1st January 2022 to 31st January 2023).

To test the possibilities of transfer learning for traffic state prediction, two additional open datasets were collected, from two different cities:

1. Los Angeles (US)

The METR-LA dataset [12], including counts on the highway of Los Angeles, is commonly used in literature for benchmarking methods on traffic state prediction.

2. Luzern (Switzerland)

The UTD19 dataset [13] is a large-scale traffic dataset from detectors on urban roads in 40 cities worldwide. Luzern is one of them, and contains traffic flows, from loop detectors, in three-minute time stamps.

Both datasets are very different, as the METR-LA dataset, only contains speed data on highways, while UTD19 contains urban data. As a result, the METR-LA

Fig. 3 Location of loop detectors in Greater Manchester

dataset is smooth and cleaned, while the UTD19 urban traffic flows change very abruptly.

The three datasets allowed for some explorative tests on transfer learning for traffic state predictions. Two different sets of tests were performed: one to predict traffic counts (see Table 1), and one to predict traffic speeds (see Table 2)). For counts and speed two models were trained: a classic traffic state prediction model that was trained on historical data from Manchester and made predictions for Manchester; a transfer learning model that was trained on historical data from either LA or Luzern and made predictions for Manchester. The preliminary results are presented in the tables below, including details regarding the amount of data used in both the source and target city, and error measurements in preliminary testing. In tables, Mean Absolute Error (MAE) measures the average of the absolute differences between prediction and ground truths. Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) measures the average percentages errors between predictions and ground truths. Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (SMAPE) is a symmetric variation of MAPE and is bounded between 0% and 200% and is useful when the ground truths has small values. Finally Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) Measures the square root of the average of squared differences between predictions and ground truths.

Table 1 Comparison fully trained and transferred model on counts of target city Greater Manchester

	Fully trained traffic state prediction (count) model	Transfer learning from Luzern to Manchester
Source city	Greater Manchester	Luzern
Amount of data of source city used (for training)	9 months	8.4 months
Target city	Greater Manchester	Greater Manchester
Amount of data of target city used (for training/finetuning)	9 months	23 days
MAE	6.806 cars/5 minutes	10.674 cars/5 minutes
MAPE	0.4496	0.9752
SMAPE	0.3406	0.5632
RMSE	52.906	31.8771

These results are promising, as the difference in mean absolute errors between the classic and transfer learning methods is not substantial. Bear in mind that with transfer learning the applied models have seen less historical data of the cities (23 days compared to several months in these tests), in this case Greater Manchester, while they are still able to get comparable results to the classic method. The difference in mean absolute errors is the smallest for speed, which might be caused by the statistical distribution of this data. Even, in extremis, when starting from a trained model on a highway dataset (METR-LA) we still achieve promising results with transfer learning for traffic speeds in the urban area of Manchester.

Table 2 Comparison fully trained and transferred model on speeds of target city Greater Manchester

	Fully trained traffic state pre-diction (speed)	Transfer learning from Los Angeles to Manchester
Source city	Greater Manchester	Los Angeles
Amount of data of source city used (for training)	9 months	3 months
Target city	Greater Manchester	Greater Manchester
Amount of data of target city used (for training/finetuning)	9 months	23 days
MAE	1.929 mph	1.928 mph
MAPE	0.1667	0.1556
SMAPE	0.1881	0.1965
RMSE	5.198	6.7326

3.2 Case study of Lisbon

Another use case in the TANGENT project focuses on Lisbon. For this case study, we utilize a dataset containing traffic speed and count data on 8 loop detectors from A5 motorway. The dataset has a 5 minute resolution and covers a period of 1 year 9 months, from January 1st 2022, to September 30th 2023. Similar to the Greater Manchester case study, we apply transfer learning techniques using the METR-LA dataset for traffic speed and the UTD19 dataset for traffic count. The preliminary results are presented in tables 3 and 4, which follow a similar structure as the Greater Manchester case study.

Table 3 Comparison fully trained and transferred model on counts of target city Lisbon

	Fully trained traffic state pre-diction (count)	Transfer learning from Luzern to Lisbon
Source city	Lisbon	Luzern
Amount of data of source city used (for training)	14.7 months	8.4 months
Target city	Lisbon	Lisbon
Amount of data of target city used (for training/finetuning)	14.7 months	1.6 months
MAE	19.961 cars/5 minutes	44.561 cars/5 minutes
MAPE	0.1636	0.7584
SMAPE	0.1412	0.3569
RMSE	31.626	58.594

The preliminary results show that the transfer learning model for traffic speed is working a bit better than the fully trained prediction models. However, it performs poorly with the traffic count predictions model in Lisbon. We observed that the mean daily count for Luzern is 10.958 cars per day, while it is 49.751 cars per day for Lisbon. The mean daily count for Manchester is 10.818 cars per day which can explain

superior accuracy in Manchester. This is due to the fact that the Lisbon dataset only contains locations on a motorway, while Luzern and Manchester contain a diverse set of various road types. Section 3.3 explains future research directions how we tend to tackle this problem.

Table 4 Comparison fully trained and transferred model on speeds of target city Lisbon

	Fully trained traffic state prediction (speed)	Transfer learning from Los Angeles to Lisbon
Source city	Lisbon	Los Angeles
Amount of data of source city used (for training)	14.7 months	3 months
Target city	Lisbon	Lisbon
Amount of data of target city used (for training/finetuning)	14.7 months	1.6 months
MAE	5.941 kph	5.556 kph
MAPE	0.1338	0.1550
SMAPE	0.0950	0.0889
RMSE	11.723	10.437

3.3 Future research – towards CitCom.ai

The preliminary tests performed in the TANGENT project showed promising results, which will be further investigated in CitCom.ai. Many Flemish cities have now taken steps towards a data-driven policy. The city of Bruges, for example, has collected a lot of traffic count data during the VLOED projects. Also, the city of Genk has a strong focus on data, and captures a lot of real-time data such as parking occupancy in car parks and on the street with a scanning vehicle. The city of Mechelen, as a medium-sized city, also aspires a digital transformation but currently lacks the data for traffic state prediction. The preliminary results of the Manchester use case in TANGENT show that the data of Bruges and Genk could be used for traffic state predictions in Mechelen, through transfer learning.

Where the focus in TANGENT was on motorized traffic, the focus in CitCom.ai will be on active modes. Incorporating active modes such as walking and cycling into traffic prediction models presents unique challenges and opportunities. Active modes contribute significantly to urban mobility but have different patterns and requirements compared to motorized traffic. Accurate prediction of these modes can enhance traffic management by providing a holistic view of urban movement, thereby improving infrastructure planning and safety measures. The integration of crowd dynamics further enriches the predictive capabilities, addressing the complexities of human movement in dense urban areas. The following research questions will be tackled in the CitCom.ai project:

- How to incorporate data from multiple cities?

- Which external features can improve the predictive model (e.g., weather, public transport data, cashless payments, etc.)?
- How can we maintain the balance between feature relevance and model generalizability? How about generalizability that might get lost by taking too many details in external features into account?
- As the tests regarding transfer learning in the TANGENT project were preliminary, a complete validation with e.g., bin statistics, visualizations, etc. was not included. To further investigate transfer learning, these insights are however required to give a better perspective towards small and medium-sized cities.
- Referring to the issues presented with transferring to Lisbon in Section 3.2, how to adapt the methodology to work with scenarios where the source dataset has a different distribution than the target dataset? We will investigate domain adaptation methods such as feature alignment or domain-invariant feature learning, as they have shown promising results in previous research.

These research questions resulted from limitations we faced during the analysis of the preliminary results with different distributions, e.g., how to deal with various datasets, how to deal with challenges related to data compatibility, particularly in reference to external features, etc.

4 Conclusion

In summary, research conducted as part of the TANGENT project highlights the feasibility, challenges and benefits of using transfer learning to predict traffic states in data-scarce regions. This promotes more efficient and scalable traffic management solutions, accommodating diverse urban transportation modes and dynamics, and enhancing the overall mobility experience in cities. The method will be further explored for the city of Mechelen in the CitCom.ai project where we will tackle the challenges that we addressed in this paper together with challenges that are common in transfer learning.

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